

NOTES TO UNDERSTAND OPEN SCIENCE A LITTLE BETTER

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For some time, I had been keen to catch up on what open science really means and how research data are shared. As I have read and learnt more, I have felt the need to organise some ideas and, above all, to share them. What follows is not a closed or exhaustive text, but rather a set of notes, observations and brief reflections “in the open”, developed as I explore this field, which is as complex as it is fascinating.

WHAT IS OPEN SCIENCE?

Open science is a transformative way of understanding scientific research. It is gaining momentum around the world and involves an important shift in the way we think about, conduct and share research.

This approach seeks to make science more accessible, transparent and collaborative, breaking down barriers and opening the doors of knowledge to everyone. Even so, there are still many uncertainties about what “open science” actually means, which can make it difficult to put into practice.

To clarify the concept, different institutions and experts have proposed definitions. One of the most prominent is that of UNESCO¹, which defines open science as “an inclusive approach that brings together different movements and practices with three broad aims: to make scientific knowledge available, accessible and reusable for everyone; to promote collaboration and information sharing for the benefit of both science and society; and to open scientific processes to the participation of other societal actors, beyond the research community”. This definition places the emphasis on a form of science that is more approachable and socially relevant.

The definition proposed by Vicente-Sáez and Martínez-Fuentes is also relevant². It was developed after reviewing 75 academic and institutional publications. These authors

¹UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO.
<https://doi.org/10.54677/mnmh8546>

²Vicente-Saez, R., & Martinez-Fuentes, C. (2018). Open Science now: A systematic literature review for an integrated definition. *Journal of Business Research*, 88, 428-436.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusres.2017.12.043>

suggest understanding open science as “transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks”. According to these researchers, open science is based on four fundamental principles concerning knowledge:

- **Transparency:** explaining how research is carried out and how decisions are made.
- **Accessibility:** enabling everyone to access knowledge without barriers.
- **Sharing:** opening up data, results, tools and methods so that others can reuse them.
- **Collaborative work:** conducting research through networks, with other researchers, institutions and also with citizens.

This approach includes practices such as open access to scientific articles, the publication of open data, the sharing of open-source code and scripts used for data analysis, citizen science, open peer review, and the use of collaborative digital tools. Taken together, it is an approach that can contribute to research that is fairer, more efficient, reproducible and useful to society.

Although they share a common core, the definitions offered by UNESCO and by Vicente-Sáez and Martínez-Fuentes include some nuances. UNESCO places greater emphasis on social participation and the global transformative potential of open science, whereas Vicente-Sáez and Martínez-Fuentes offer a more structured and analytical view. Far from being contradictory, these two perspectives are complementary: one helps us to understand what open science is, while the other provides guidance on how to put it into practice.

Key concept

Open science is a way of conducting research that seeks to make knowledge open to everyone: by sharing data, results and processes, and by involving society in the scientific process.

OPEN SCIENCE PRACTICES

Open science is not only an idea, but a concrete way of generating knowledge that is more transparent, accessible, collaborative and shared. This means that not only experts, but also members of the public, can see how research is conducted, access its results, take part in it and reuse what has already been done. Building on the four principles described above (see Figure 1), we can see how they translate into everyday research practices.

Transparency: showing how research is carried out

Making science transparent means explaining what is being done, how and why, from the beginning to the end of the process. This may include sharing the research plan from the outset, for example through preregistration; documenting how data have been collected and analysed; or publishing results, even when they are not definitive. Transparency builds trust and makes it easier for others to understand and reproduce the research..

Figure 1. Conceptual basis of open science²

Accessibility: enabling everyone to access knowledge

This principle argues that knowledge should not be limited by financial or institutional barriers. In practice, this means publishing articles, data or code openly, and following criteria such as the FAIR principles^{3,4}, which promote data that are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

Sharing: opening up knowledge for reuse

³ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., Da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

⁴ CORA – Àrea de Recerca Oberta de Catalunya. (s.f.). *Què són dades FAIR?* Consorci de Serveis Universitaris de Catalunya (CSUC). <https://cora.csuc.cat/dades-fair/que-son-dades-fair/>

Sharing is not only about making something visible; it means making what has been created available so that others can use, analyse or adapt it. Opening up data, code or protocols enables research to move forward more rapidly and collectively.

Collaborative work: doing science with more people

Open research is committed to working with other people and sectors, beyond academic and research settings. This includes interdisciplinary and institutional collaborations, as well as citizen science initiatives, recognising that knowledge is built more effectively when it incorporates diverse perspectives.

Key concepts

Transparency and sharing: they are not the same thing! It is easy to confuse these two terms, but they refer to different things:

- **Transparency shows us how a study has been carried out: it is like opening the kitchen and showing the process.**
- **Sharing allows us to use what has been cooked: it is letting other people taste the dish, make copies or add new ingredients.**

Ultimately, one thing is to see the process, and another is to have access to the results so that they can be used.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN OPEN SCIENCE

Adopting open science practices brings many benefits, but it also entails responsibilities. Opening up knowledge requires us to ensure respect for people, their data and the contexts in which those data are generated.

Protecting people and their data

When research involves personal data, it is necessary to ensure that participants cannot be identified. This means applying anonymisation or pseudonymisation techniques that reduce the risk of re-identification, while maintaining the scientific value of the data. Finding the right balance between protecting privacy and preserving analytical value is one of the major challenges of open science

What are personal data?

Personal data (see Table 1) are any type of information that can identify a person. Some data can identify a person directly, while others may do so when combined with other

information. Within this broad category, there are special categories of personal data that are particularly sensitive and require enhanced protection.

Table 1. Types of personal data

Type of data	Examples
Personal data	Age, gender, national identity number, biometric data, address, postcode, etc.
Educational data	Qualifications, level of education, etc.
Contact details	Telephone number, email address, social media profiles, etc.
Financial data	Monthly income, bank account number, etc.
Health data	Diagnoses, diagnostic test results, healthcare identification number, etc.
Special categories of personal data	Racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, data concerning sex life or sexual orientation, etc.

How are data anonymised?

Anonymisation techniques are used to make it more difficult to identify individuals in a dataset. Some of the most common are:

- **Generalisation:** this involves making data less precise. For example, transforming “26 years old” into “[20–30 years old]”. This protects identity while preserving analytical value.

👉 Aim: to hide the detail while maintaining usefulness.

- **Suppression:** this involves removing sensitive data that could easily identify a person. For example, if a dataset includes only one person who is a man, aged 25, and has a low educational level, this combination makes him identifiable. In this case, the “education” field could be removed to protect him.

👉 Aim: to prevent uncommon data from revealing identities.

- **Perturbation:** this involves slightly modifying values to add “noise”. If a person earns €1,052, this could be shown as €1,070. This prevents direct re-identification.

👉 Aim: to obscure the data without removing useful information.

How do we know whether the dataset is safe?

Applying techniques is very helpful, but how can we know whether they actually work? This is where privacy models come in. These models act as mathematical criteria to check whether the level of protection is adequate. The two best known are:

- **k-anonymity**: this ensures that each record is “similar” to at least $k-1$ other individuals. If $k = 5$, this means that each combination of data appears at least five times, and that the probability of identifying someone is only 1 in 5.

👉 Aim: to protect direct identity.

- **l-diversity**: in addition to k-anonymity, this requires sensitive data to also be diverse within each group. For example, if everyone in a group has the same disease, privacy is not well protected.

👉 Aim: to protect against the disclosure of sensitive values.

Although these techniques and models do not guarantee absolute protection, they do significantly reduce the risk that someone could identify the people behind the data. In open science contexts, where sharing is key to scientific progress, protecting privacy is not optional: it is an ethical and legal responsibility⁵.

Fortunately, there are open-source tools that can help apply these techniques, such as:

- ARX Data Anonymization Tool⁶
- Amnesia, developed as part of the European ATHENA project⁷

However, the tool does not do the work on its own: training, clear protocols and good practices are also needed. Open science is only legitimate if it respects the fundamental rights of participants. Far from being an obstacle, data protection strengthens research when it is applied with transparency, appropriate tools and ethical commitment.

⁵In the European and Spanish contexts, this responsibility is framed, among others, by Regulation (EU) 2016/679 –the General Data Protection Regulation, GDPR– and by Organic Law 3/2018 on the Protection of Personal Data and the Guarantee of Digital Rights.

⁶ARX – Data Anonymization Tool. (s. f.). arx.deidentifier.org. Retrieved 24 July 2025, from <https://arx.deidentifier.org>

⁷OpenAIRE. (s. f.). *Amnesia – Data Anonymization*. Retrieved 24 July 2025, from <https://amnesia.openaire.eu>

Key concepts

Anonymisation techniques are different ways of obscuring or protecting data so that they remain useful for research or management purposes, while avoiding risks to people's privacy.

Privacy models are like safety rules that indicate whether a dataset is sufficiently protected against attacks or inferences. They should be applied together with anonymisation techniques to ensure that people's information remains private, even when the data are used for research or statistics.

Informed consent and open science

Open science has a very clear aim: to ensure that the knowledge generated through research is accessible, transparent and useful for everyone. Not only for other scientists, but also for professionals, policymakers and, above all, the public. To make this possible, data and results need to be shared in a way that is safe, clear and respectful of the people who take part.

When a study collects data from people, participants must know how those data will be used and for what purpose. This is what we call informed consent: a process through which each participant understands what is being studied, how their data will be used, what benefits or risks participation may involve, and whether those data will be shared, for example, in open repositories. Only when this information has been properly understood and accepted freely and voluntarily can we speak of ethically valid consent.

However, in many current projects –particularly in research that follows an open and long-term approach, such as biobanks or other studies with future purposes that have not yet been fully defined– it is common practice to use what is known as broad consent⁸. In other words, participants are asked to give their permission within a previously defined general framework, allowing their data and samples to be used in future studies linked to the same area or line of research, even if those studies have not yet been fully specified at the time consent is given.

Broad consent should not be confused with “blanket” consent or with fully open practices. In theory, it does not authorise any future use, but only those uses linked to a previously

⁸Maloy, J. W., & Bass, P. F. (2020). Understanding Broad Consent. *Ochsner Journal*, 20(1), 81-86.
<https://doi.org/10.31486/toj.19.0088>

defined research area and subject to an ethical and governance framework. This framework includes, among other aspects, review by independent research ethics committees, privacy protection measures and the possibility of withdrawing consent. If this framework is modified, or if proposed uses fall outside it, new explicit consent should be obtained.

Even so, this model has been the subject of intense academic and ethical debate⁹. Different voices have questioned whether it can truly be considered “informed” consent, since many of the future studies to which access would be granted are not yet defined or foreseeable at the initial stage. For some authors, the expression “broad informed consent” is, in itself, a contradiction. It has even been argued that these models may limit people’s ability to fully exercise their fundamental rights and freedoms. These criticisms, together with technological advances that now allow more fluid and bidirectional digital communication with participants, have led to a reconsideration of the use of broad consent, particularly in research that seeks to remain consistent with the principles of open science and public participation.

In response to these challenges, an innovative alternative has emerged: dynamic consent¹⁰. This approach uses digital technology to offer a more flexible and participatory model.

Rather than requesting consent only once, at the beginning of the study, dynamic consent allows participants to access, review and modify their decisions at any time through a personalised digital platform. In addition, they receive updated information about the project and can decide which future studies they do or do not wish to take part in.

This approach has shown clear benefits:

- It improves participants’ experience, as they can tailor their involvement according to their preferences and retain control over their data.
- It increases trust and engagement, thanks to more direct and ongoing communication with the research team.
- It promotes more inclusive participation, as geographical and language barriers can be overcome.

⁹Steinsbekk, K. S., Kåre Myskja, B., & Solberg, B. (2013). Broad consent versus dynamic consent in biobank research: Is passive participation an ethical problem? *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 21(9), 897–902. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ejhg.2012.282>

¹⁰Lay, W., Gasparini, L., Siero, W., & Hughes, E. K. (2025). A rapid review of the benefits and challenges of dynamic consent. *Research Ethics*, 21(1), 180–202. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17470161241278064>

- It may simplify administrative management, making the data collection process more efficient.

However, it also presents important challenges. Not everyone has easy access to devices or an internet connection, and people with low digital literacy could be excluded. Providing too many options may also feel overwhelming for some participants, and in digital environments it is not always easy to verify a person's identity securely. In addition, although some practical experiences already exist, robust evidence on how to implement this model in a sustainable and accessible way for everyone is still limited.

In summary, dynamic consent offers a flexible and innovative framework that can improve not only consent management, but also the quality of the relationship between participants and research teams. Beyond enabling a more personalised and participatory experience, these digital platforms can incorporate useful features, such as ongoing communication or data collection over time. Although there are limitations, such as unequal access to technology or information overload, several studies—for example, the CHRIS study¹¹—have found ways to reduce their impact by combining this model with more traditional options and adapting the level of interaction to each person's preferences. Dynamic consent therefore emerges as a promising strategy, aligned with the values of open science, which can contribute to research that is more respectful, transparent and inclusive.

Key concepts

Before taking part in a study, each person must know what is being investigated, how their data will be used, and whether those data will be shared. This is what ensures genuinely free and ethical consent.

Dynamic consent is a new model that allows people to review and modify their consent whenever they wish, through a digital platform, fostering research that is more open, flexible and centred on people.

Justice and equity in access and participation

Open science aims to make knowledge more accessible and useful for everyone, but this is only possible if we take into account the inequalities that exist both within and beyond the

¹¹Pattaro, C., Pramstaller, P., Hicks, A., & Teare, H. J. A. (2022). Ten years of dynamic consent in the CHRIS study. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 30(9), 947–955. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-022-01160-4>

research world. Opening up data and results does not, in itself, guarantee that everyone will be able to access them or participate on equal terms. As Cole and colleagues remind us¹², open science may reinforce injustices if it does not explicitly address differences in technological, linguistic and territorial access. For example, people or institutions without a good internet connection, without digital resources, or without proficiency in English – the dominant language of scientific publication – may be left outside the benefits of open science.

This inequality also shapes the participation of vulnerable or minoritised communities, which are often absent from the spaces where scientific priorities are decided. A truly inclusive model of open science must enable these communities not only to access information, but also to participate in and influence the scientific process. Along these lines, the “Manifesto for a globally diverse, equitable and inclusive open science”¹³ states that research should incorporate diverse populations, contexts and cultural perspectives –and make them transparent– to prevent conclusions from being based on biased knowledge and ultimately representing only a small part of the world. Indeed, the manifesto introduces the concept of MASKing (Making Assumptions based on Skewed Knowledge), which describes how researchers may, often without realising it, base theories, methods or interpretations on biased or poorly representative knowledge. This phenomenon occurs when samples, measures or research questions themselves reflect only a partial view of the world, and may lead to conclusions that are not useful for many other communities or realities.

Finally, open science must pay attention to a risk that has been widely debated in recent years: data colonialism¹⁴. When data are collected in countries, communities or minoritised groups and are later used –or commercialised– by institutions with scientific or economic power, an unequal relationship is perpetuated, even if the data are “open”. Opening up data without responsibility may enable other actors to appropriate knowledge without returning any benefit to the communities that generated it. As Ghai and colleagues warn¹³, open science must ensure that generosity in data sharing does not become a new form of extraction or dispossession.

¹²Cole, N. L., Reichmann, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2023). Toward equitable open research: Stakeholder co-created recommendations for research institutions, funders and researchers. *Royal Society Open Science*, 10(2), 221460. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.221460>

¹³Ghai, S., Thériault, R., Forscher, P., Shoda, Y., Syed, M., Puthillam, A., Peng, H. C., Basnight-Brown, D., Majid, A., Azevedo, F., & Singh, L. (2025). A manifesto for a globally diverse, equitable, and inclusive open science. *Communications Psychology*, 3(1), 16. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44271-024-00179-1>

¹⁴McCutchan, S. (2022). Research data governance for global health. *Duke Global Health Institute*. Disponible a: https://globalhealth.duke.edu/sites/default/files/files/ghdatagov_landscapeanalysisv1.1.pdf

Key concept

Opening up knowledge does not guarantee equity: it is necessary to ensure that all people and communities can access, participate and have influence without inequalities.

Integrity, responsibility and traceability

One of the pillars of open science is ensuring that the entire research process is traceable, honest and responsible. This involves not only sharing data or results, but also showing transparently how they have been generated. As Munafò and colleagues note¹⁵, this transparency is essential to strengthen the credibility of research and to support its reproduction and verification by other researchers.

A first ethical commitment is the preregistration of studies and the careful documentation of procedures. Recording hypotheses, methods and analysis plans in advance helps to reduce the analytical flexibility that can distort results. As Nosek and colleagues emphasise¹⁶, preregistration is a key tool for avoiding post hoc interpretations and for ensuring clear tracking of the scientific process.

Open science also seeks to prevent unethical practices, such as the manipulation of analyses, the selective reporting of results or the concealment of negative findings. This last point is particularly important: the non-publication of non-significant results creates a systematic bias that affects the accumulation of knowledge. Franco and colleagues¹⁷ showed that many studies remain “in the file drawer” simply because they do not present positive results, and that sharing them is essential for honest and efficient science.

Finally, another key aspect is the fair recognition of all contributions. In collective projects, it is necessary to make visible the work of everyone who has taken part, including tasks that are often invisible, such as data curation, code development or project management.

¹⁵Munafò, M. R., Nosek, B. A., Bishop, D. V. M., Button, K. S., Chambers, C. D., Percie Du Sert, N., Simonsohn, U., Wagenmakers, E.-J., Ware, J. J., & Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2017). A manifesto for reproducible science. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 1(1), 0021. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-016-0021>

¹⁶Nosek, B. A., Ebersole, C. R., DeHaven, A. C., & Mellor, D. T. (2018). The preregistration revolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 115(11), 2600–2606. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1708274114>

¹⁷Franco, A., Malhotra, N., & Simonovits, G. (2014). Publication bias in the social sciences: Unlocking the file drawer. *Science*, 345(6203), 1502–1505. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1255484>

Taxonomies such as CRediT¹⁸ offer a useful framework for assigning credit in a clear, transparent and equitable way.

Overall, integrity, responsibility and traceability are not merely technical requirements: they are ethical conditions that make more reliable, fair and socially useful science possible.

Key concept

Open science is transparent throughout the entire process, not only in its results.

Ethical collaboration and mutual respect

Open science is not only about sharing data or results, but also about how we work together. Conducting research openly means building relationships based on respect, trust and justice among everyone involved: researchers, institutions, social organisations and the public.

Ethical collaboration means that no one is excluded from important decisions. All parties should know what is being done, why it is being done, and how the data or results will be used. When decisions are made jointly, research becomes fairer and more socially relevant¹⁹.

This is especially important to avoid unfair forms of research, in which a community contributes data, time or knowledge but receives nothing in return. The literature on community collaboration shows that a lack of return can generate mistrust and reproduce inequalities¹⁷.

In the case of citizen science, this principle is essential. Participants should not be treated merely as “sources of data”, but as active members of the project. As Bonney and colleagues²⁰ show, citizen science projects work better when they provide feedback on results, communicate clearly and offer genuine recognition of participation.

¹⁸National Information Standards Organization. (2022). CRediT – Contributor Roles Taxonomy. <https://credit.niso.org>

¹⁹Wallerstein N. Engage for Equity: Advancing the Fields of Community-Based Participatory Research and Community-engaged Research in Community Psychology and the Social Sciences. *American J of Comm Psychol.* 2021;67:251-5. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajcp.12530>

²⁰Bonney R, Phillips TB, Ballard HL, Enck JW. Can citizen science enhance public understanding of science? *Public Underst Sci.* 2016;25:2-16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662515607406>

In summary, ethical collaboration in open science is based on a very simple idea: working together means respecting one another, listening to one another and sharing benefits. When this is achieved, science becomes fairer, more useful and closer to society.

Key concept

Open science is grounded in equitable and transparent collaborations, oriented towards the mutual benefit of all parties involved.

Social impact and the responsible use of knowledge

One of the major aims of open science is to ensure that the knowledge it generates has a positive impact on society. However, opening up data and results may also involve risks if it is not done carefully. For this reason, several international frameworks emphasise that open science must always be accompanied by responsibility and ethical reflection²¹.

One of the main risks is the misuse of open data, particularly when sensitive data are involved, such as health data or personal information. Even when data have been anonymised, they may be reused out of context or combined with other sources, leading to misleading interpretations or risks for the people and communities involved. As Leonelli notes²², data openness is not neutral: the way data are reused can have unforeseen social consequences.

For this reason, open science supports a widely accepted key principle: “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. This approach recognises that not all data should be shared in the same way or with the same level of access. According to the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), openness must be balanced with the protection of rights, privacy, security, and respect for social and cultural contexts.

The social impact of open science also depends on how results are communicated. Communication that is unclear or overly simplified may generate confusion, alarmism or inappropriate uses of knowledge. Responsible science communication involves explaining results in an understandable way, while also making explicit their limitations, uncertainties and potential misuses.

²¹UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO.

<https://doi.org/10.54677/mnmh8546>

²²Leonelli S. Why the Current Insistence on Open Access to Scientific Data? Big Data, Knowledge Production, and the Political Economy of Contemporary Biology. *Bulletin of Science, Technology & Society*. 2013;33:6-11. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0270467613496768>

Overall, open science has great transformative potential, but this potential only becomes a reality when knowledge is shared and used responsibly, carefully and in pursuit of the common good.

Key concept

Opening up knowledge also means taking responsibility for its social impact.

FINAL REFLECTIONS

These notes are not intended to be a manual, but rather a starting point. Open science is a way of conducting research that is learnt through practice: by sharing, documenting and engaging in thoughtful dialogue. If I had to keep just one idea, it would be this: opening up science has great potential, but it only works well when it is done with respect, responsibility and a genuine commitment to including everyone. It is not a fixed recipe, but a practice that is built step by step.

Implementing open science also has costs. It requires time, resources and institutional support. For this reason, it cannot depend solely on individual willingness, but requires changes in the training, incentives and infrastructures that sustain research.

SOME PRACTICAL RESOURCES

To conclude, I have brought together a set of useful resources to help start putting open science into practice in everyday work. These are diverse tools –from repositories and support platforms to guidelines, protocols and international initiatives– that can support data management, as well as data sharing, anonymisation and preservation.

Ada Lovelace Institute

An independent centre working to ensure that data and artificial intelligence (AI) serve social wellbeing. The Institute argues that the benefits of these technologies should be distributed fairly and gives voice to people who are often excluded from the debate. Through research and public policy, it promotes the responsible and human-centred use of AI.

 <https://www.adalovelaceinstitute.org/about/>

Amnesia – Data Anonymization

Tool developed within the European ATHENA project, designed for the anonymisation of datasets.

 <https://amnesia.openaire.eu>

ARX Data Anonymization Tool

A comprehensive open-source tool for data anonymisation. It allows users to apply privacy models and provides a graphical interface, so it can be used without the need for programming.

 <https://arx.deidentifier.org>

CORA – FAIR data

A clear explanation of what FAIR data are, with resources to help start applying them.

 <https://cora.csuc.cat/en/what-is-fair-data/>

CRedit – Contributor Roles Taxonomy

A tool that clearly describes each person's contributions to a research project. It helps recognise tasks that are often invisible –such as data curation, code development, supervision or methodology– and promotes a fairer and more transparent distribution of credit within teams.

 <https://credit.niso.org>

Dryad

An open-access digital repository specifically designed for sharing research datasets. All datasets published in it are reviewed, assigned a DOI and can be easily reused. It is a useful tool for accompanying scientific articles with their associated data.

<https://datadryad.org>

FAIR Toolkit – Pistoia Alliance

A practical resource offering guidelines, tools and concrete examples to help implement the FAIR principles in research data management. It is particularly useful for moving from theory to action.

 <https://fairtoolkit.pistoiaalliance.org>

Figshare

A repository for openly publishing any type of research material, including data, figures, videos, protocols and more.

 <https://figshare.com>

GitHub

A widely used platform for sharing code, analysis scripts and data with version control. It allows changes in a project to be documented and tracked transparently.

 <https://github.com>

GO FAIR

An international community offering documentation and training to support the implementation of FAIR strategies at institutional or project level.

 <https://www.go-fair.org>

medRxiv

A preprint server for the health sciences that allows preliminary research findings to be shared before peer review. It is designed to promote transparency, the rapid dissemination of knowledge and the collective improvement of studies through open comments.

 <https://www.medrxiv.org>

OpenAIRE

A network of repositories and services for tracking the outputs of publicly funded research in Europe.

 <https://www.openaire.eu>

OSF–Open Science Framework

A free platform for preregistering research protocols, sharing documents and managing projects in an open and collaborative way.

 <https://osf.io>

The Turing Way

An open and collaborative guide to good practices in computational science, including how to share code effectively.

 <https://book.the-turing-way.org>

UNESCO Open Science Toolkit

A practical resource that brings together clear and useful materials to help institutions and research teams apply open science. It includes guidelines, recommendations and

factsheets that are updated regularly and developed collaboratively with experts and UNESCO working groups to respond to the real challenges of scientific openness.

 <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/toolkit>

Zenodo (promoted by CERN and the European Commission)

It allows users to share data, protocols, code and preprints, each with its own DOI.

<https://zenodo.org>